

Exploring the nexus between Nigeria waterways, national and international security

Paul Terlumun Bemgba ^{1,*}, Ene Vincent-Orugbo ¹, Dube, Philemon Abrak ², Lawanson Joseph ³ and Leawat Jesse James ⁴

¹ *Legislative Centre for Security Analysis (LeCeSA), National Institute for Legislative and Democratic Studies (NILDS), National Assembly, Abuja, Nigeria.*

² *Institute of Governance and development studies, Nasarawa State University, Keffi (NSUK), Abuja, Nigeria.*

³ *Department of Intelligence and Security Science, Faculty of Military Science, Nigeria Defence Academy, Kaduna State, Abuja, Nigeria.*

⁴ *Center for Conflict Management and Peace Studies, University of Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.*

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Abstract

The existence and sustainability of humanity on earth have been linked to numerous human economic activities which have precipitated the movement of people, goods, and services across various geographical climes. These economic activities over time have impacted the maritime ecosystem and have been identified as one of the most influential means of interactions in trade and commercial activities as it accounts for over 90% of the global movement of goods and services as against other means and forms of transportation. It is in light that this study looked at the impact of waterways on Nigeria's economy, the nexus between waterways, national and international security and maritime threats to Nigeria waterways. The study adopted the secondary method of data collection through content analysis of online publications, journals, news items, government gazettes, unpublished theses, etc. Using the Marxist political economic theory popularized by Adam Smith and David Ricardo in the 18th century, this study found out that the Nigeria maritime sector is a vital component of the country's economy, contributing significantly to its GDP and employing thousands of workers. However, the industry is plagued by severe maritime threats, including piracy, sea robbery, and maritime terrorism, which are attributed to various factors such as socio-economic, political, and infrastructural deficits. This study concluded by recommending that the Nigerian government should enhance Indigenous participation and domination in the maritime sector, strengthen maritime security and surveillance, and implement international frameworks and guidelines.

Keywords: Nigeria National Waterways; National Security; International Security; Maritime Threats

1. Introduction

The earth is made up of three key elements namely; land, air, and water. Out of these three-elements water covers about 71 percent of the earth which is about 0.02 percent of the total planet mass. The ocean holds about 96.5 percent of all earth water, others include rivers, lakes. Similarly, water also exists in the air in the form of water vapour, icecaps, and glaciers (<https://olc.worldbank.org/>). The essentiality of water to humanity cannot be underestimated. Proliferation of water bodies across the earth in terms of rivers, lakes, sea, and the ocean has been instrumental to the survival of humanity on planet earth. The large water body serves as a source of employment through fishing, transportation, and forms of protections in the engagement of hostile forces or platforms for invasions. Nonetheless, the spatial distribution of water bodies has influenced economic interaction and communication of human beings, Nation-states, and organizations. Historically, the waterways have immensely contributed to the enhancement and projecting of military power and used for the pursuance of national and international relations among states in the international system. Not

* Corresponding author: Bemgba Paul Terlumun

without doubt, hegemonic wars that shaped the international system were largely conducted within the large straits of waterways with notable events of the Second World War such as the invasion of Iwo-Jima, the defeat of the German U-boats along the Mediterranean Sea and the allied invasion of Normandy which was one of the major highlights of allied theatre operations that brought an end to the second world war.

Today, the large straits of waterways are indeed a major player in the sustainability of the global economic system. It is said that over 90 percent of the global trade (in dry and wet goods) is sustained by the maritime ecosystem. Global transportation of goods and services relies purposefully on the systematic lines of communication of the maritime world to transport goods from one continent to the other. Likewise, sovereign states in the pursuit of their various global and economic trade interactions depend on the instrumentality of the maritime sector in boosting their national development. This accentuates the important role played by the maritime ecosystem in aiding sustainable growth and development in both national and international spheres.

With the waterways becoming more exponential in their activities, and the extreme reliance on its activities by both developed and developing states for their own national and economic survival cannot be underestimated. Similarly, the threats posed to the safety of the maritime sector and waterways have become more conspicuous, outrageous, and lethal. Major economic exclusive zones (EER) around the world are on the verge of total collapse due to security threats and their actors are increasingly gaining a foothold on the economic activities within such zones (Ifedi, 2020, p.224). Also, maritime shipping is not left out of the threat scare as threat actors now lay siege along the international shipping routes to attack vessels for economic gain. The international shipping routes which include: the strait of Malacca, Indonesian water, the Gulf of Aden, and the Gulf of Guinea are progressively becoming dangerous and target centric by threat actors aiming at hijacking shipping vessels for economic advantage (Ifedi, 2020). Out of all the potential shipping areas within the maritime ecosystem, the waterways in Africa present itself as a strategic maritime area for trade and investment due to its vast consumable market for commodities and presence of consumers.

The Gulf of Guinea is primarily a major waterway trade route in Africa, and it represents about 25 percent of Africa maritime traffic, with twenty commercial seaports covering an area of about 6,000km of coastline used in the transportation hydrocarbon resources, cargo goods within and outside Africa, and plays host to numerous fishing activities (Morcos, 2021).

Despite having enormous economic and trade activities carried out across its waterways The gulf has been challenged by numerous security problems. These security problems include threats such as inter-state maritime disputes, maritime terrorism, piracy, trafficking of narcotics, people and illicit goods, arms proliferation, illegal fishing, environmental crimes, maritime accidents, and disasters. The task of combating these threats both at the international and national level have become significant in providing protection to the volume of economic activities carried out vis-à-vis the water ways. Furthermore, national, and international security concern itself with the creation of a framework that can combat all forms of irregularities and security challenges posed to the sustainability of maritime transportation, trade and economic activities along international waterways and its tributaries domestically. To this end, internationally the United Nation Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and the International Maritime Organization (IMO) provides a necessary security framework in addressing the level of insecurity along international waterways. At the regional level, the Yaoundé code of conduct regional maritime security framework is used to drive home security cooperation in tackling maritime insecurity along our waterways. At the national level, countries that make up the Gulf of Guinea have domesticated the international framework into creating maritime instruments to challenge the nature of insecurity along waterways, within their domain which includes on shore and shallow waters. Also, the interjection of naval units and maritime police have also been used at the local level in curtailing the level of insecurity along our waterways.

Due to the depth of technicalities of areas of interest within the debate of the concept of maritime waterways and its varying subsectors, this study will limit its scope to the nexus on national waterways, its connection to national and international security, with the primary interest of insecurity along the waterways. This paper will be guided by the following objectives:

- To examine the impact of Waterways on Nigeria's Economy
- To find out the nexus between waterways, National and International Security.
- To analyse the maritime threats to Nigeria waterways

2. Conceptual Clarification

2.1. Concept of National Security

The concept of national security concerns itself with the protection and welfare of a state. It may be defined in terms of territorial protection, or in the interest of a sovereign political entity. Traditionally, national security has been defined in militaristic terms strictly under the auspice of defence, territorial integrity, and strategic issues. Wolfers opined the notion of national security is an “ambiguous symbol” which he stated to be deceptive and meaningless when put into use as a policy. His definition of national security connotes the “absence of threat to acquired values” (Wolfers 1965; Rahman, 2009, p.7).

According to David Dewitt (1994) tracing the traditional interest of national security was geared towards militaristic objectives alone while leaving out other aspects of national power deeming them less necessary in defining national security. However, an offset to the definitional tussle about the traditional thinking of national security was well articulated and elaborated by the United Nations Human Development Report 1994 in modelling a holistic view of national security.

The report critically examines national security from a humanistic point of view, relating human needs and government responsibility to these needs as the first step towards achieving national security. Likewise, the UN human development report explicated that national security is not far-fetched from defence and territorial protection, but at the hierarchy of security, human/ individual security is the foundation towards achieving an extensive national security objective. The UN identified and stressed the importance of other sub-structures that make up the entirety of security. This report of the society must be taken into cognizance for the actualization of National security. The UN report identifies tributaries of these sub-structures to the framework of economic security which is required, that basic income for every citizen is a necessity and should be derived from productive and remunerative work or as a last resort from a publicly financed safety net. Secondly, Food security always covers the availability of food. It is both the physical and economic access to basic food. Thirdly, health security is access to basic health care and proper nutrition. Also, environmental security covers a healthy physical environment through the eradication of threats arising from ecological degradation, water scarcity, desertification, salinity, and environmental pollution. Fourthly, personal security covers the elimination of threats from the likes of torture and intimidation, war, ethnic tension, violence, and crimes. Additionally, community security presents an essential security subset of the broader national security framework as it deals with the security of all forms of racial, ethnic, tribal, or religious affiliation. Finally, Political security caters for the survival of the sovereignty of a state, this means, every individual should be able to live a life where basic human rights are not infringed upon by the state. (Satish and Rahul, 2015, p.5).

To justify this study, the concept of national security is defined as the actualization of protection measures for citizens, territory, economy, and institutions from external and internal threats, which involves the combination of military, political, and economic efforts to prevent and respond to all forms of threat and aggression.

3. Concept of International Security

International security, also called global security, is a term which refers to the measures taken by states and international organizations, to ensure common interest, survival, and safety. These safety measures include the use of military action and diplomatic agreements such as treaties and conventions. International and national security are consistently linked as they tend to deal with the security, safety and protection of the states and their affairs in the international system. International security is a reflection of Sovereign states' national security or state security in the global arena. However, states are not the only actors in the international system, they are primary actors, as well as other substructures who are poised to work on behalf of states. Critical to international security is the formation of International governmental organizations which champion the interests of respective sovereign states and play critical roles in ensuring security to numerous societies at a varying degree, such as providing welfare, aids, political interventions, nation-building, reconstruction following conflicts, mitigating the effects of financial crises, or protecting against future environmental and health catastrophes and crafting of international laws. (Rahman, 2009, p.7).

International security is geared towards limiting occupation of anarchy, and aggression by state. Moving from purely state issues in the international system, international security also plays an important role in regulating behaviour and actions of non-state actors as they also perform important roles in shaping the international system. Multinational corporations and International governmental organizations are said to have a high degree of influence in shaping socio-political and economic objectives in the international system. Likewise, other non-state actors such as Radical terrorist

organizations, militia groups, organized crime syndicates with international colourisation have sought the interest of international security in regulating their affairs and actions to ensure a balance of security at/in the international arena.

4. Empirical Review

The review of related literature was conducted in consonance with the objective of this study

4.1. Impact of Waterways on Nigeria's Economy

Nigeria is known to be a maritime country as it is located along the vast coastline off the Gulf of Guinea and is endowed with a large strait of inland water bodies. About eighty percent (80%) of the maritime economic activities in the coast of West Africa are conducted in Nigeria. (Peretomode, 2014, p.47). It was reported that between 2009-2012, the movement of sea vessels into Nigeria was exponential, as it grew from eighty-two (82) million to one hundred and fifty (150) million with an estimated payment increase from 4.1 billion to 7.5 billion dollars. Sadly, Nigerian participation in the global maritime commercial activities is next to nothing as the country largely relies on importation rather than exportation (Peretomode, 2014, p.47). Furthermore, the reported export of Nigeria's crude oil was about nine hundred million barrels per annum, but foreign logistics and supply value chain freight profits of about USD 2.25 billion from carrying the country's crude begs the question on how we are losing revenue to foreign establishments. The overall importance of waterway to Nigeria's economy can be measured through its contribution to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) annually (Lloyd et.al, 2020: p.4). The impact has been identified to be either direct, indirect, or induced. The direct impact involves the value added to Gross Domestic Product, industry revenue and profits, among others. The indirect impact is caused by purchases occurring through direct demands on goods and services needed through the maritime sector, and the induced demand refers to demands created in the larger economy through multiplier effects such as increased purchasing power in the hands of citizens employed by the sector (Lloyd et.al, 2020: p5).

The Maritime domain serves as a channel for the industrialization growth of the Nigerian economy. It cannot be over-emphasized that every aspect of Nigeria's economy relies on the maritime sector, and it will be impossible to survive without it since it will be needed to help bring in the materials and additional services which these industries need to sustain their economic activities, materials for economic activities in a nation (Lloyd et.al, 2020: p.6). It is interesting to note that out of the global maritime transportation across various international waterways, Nigeria accounts for about ninety-five (95%) of the percent of vessel movement alone off the coast of the Gulf of Guinea (Peretomode,2014, p.48). It is revealed that 70% of industrial activities in Nigeria are sited around the port and coastal states (Badejo, 2000.; Lloyd et.al, 2020, p.5).

Maritime waterways play a fundamental role in the exploitation, distribution, and export of resources. This helps to drive to build the economic sustainability of a nation through the numerous activities and its coordinates aids in the reduction of spatial poverty and boosts national development. Nigeria's total annual freight cost is estimated between USD five billion to six billion and the Nigerian content participation is nonexistent which means something must be done to benefit from the global maritime market (Lloyd et.al, 2020, p.5). In 2010, the direct impact of maritime transportation on GDP was three (3%) percent (Olayiwola, 2010, p.534). Nigeria trades about 180 million tons of sea-borne cargo per annum. Annual freight paid was more than USD 6.8 billion, more than 80% of this revenue was earned by foreign firms in the maritime transport industry (Ekpo, 2012, p. 107).

The implication of these statistics is that Nigeria loses huge revenues to capital flights repatriated abroad by foreign maritime logistics businesses operating in the Nigeria maritime domain. In light of this development, and the loss of revenue to foreign competitors, the country should encourage Indigenous participation and domination through the local content provisions of the Cabotage Act 2003.

Furthermore, the impact of maritime transportation to the economy is seen in the employment strength as over 150,000 workers are employed in this sector and contributed in taxes to the coffers of the government estimated to be about fifteen billion dollars (Lloyd et.al, 2020, p.5). The offshore crude oil rigs and cabotage trade accounts recorded about twenty billion dollars in both import and export trade through maritime shipping in Nigeria. It is safe to state that despite the financial contribution of our waterways to the national economic growth and development, Nigeria is yet to harness the full potentials of the maritime sector economically, compared to the volume of logistics, Aquatic-agricultural activities, and the extractive sector in Nigeria.

4.2. The Nexus between Waterways, National and International Security

The interest of national and international security towards maritime activities is in relation to the entrenchment of security, the preservation of humanity and the attainment of safety from harm and injury of maritime vessels, seafarers and all economic and business activities carried out along the maritime ecosystem. At the national level, national security aims or targets the economic security and territorial integrity of our waterways. The national waterways domain makes up the territorial landscape of a state as with natural resources and aquatic habitat located within the water body. National security interest in waterways is aimed at protecting the presence of resources from undue exploitation from both non-state actors and other foreign actors. National security interest is additionally directed at harnessing such resources and developing it for the actualization of national development. The building up of militaristic strength along the waterway is a show of importance the maritime ecosystem is to a sovereign state, and to provide means of deterrence in challenging any form of threat to the survival of a state along the waterways.

Conversely, international security, despite not limited to a particular state or sovereign territory, is aimed at providing security at an holistic level to the survival of the international system from harm, threats, and aggression from an aggressive sovereign state. The maritime ecosystem has become a marketplace for the two concepts to operate side by side. With the enormous interactions in trade and investment carried out along the large straits of water bodies across the globe, the threats towards the survival of global economic activities have shaped the interest of security at the international level into establishing measures in mitigating such threats. Despite being fluid in nature, international security creates a level playing field with the use of a collective security system and an international legal instrument in setting up standards and procedures to guild against undue aggression, intimidation and pressure against trade relationship carried out along the global waterways. Additionally, the instrumentalization of collective security capability, international security is aimed at challenging any form of aggression committed against global maritime transportation routes, nations, people, and services. A key element to security at international level is also to promote global interactions and to guide affairs of economic activities carried out on international waterways.

The similitude of security objectives between national and international security is linked to ensuring a threat-free maritime ecosystem using the combination of national power mostly in militaristic terms and international framework (guidelines and procedures) in addressing all forms of threats, and the promotion of security in boosting economic collaborations among sovereign states in the maritime international system. Furthermore, this has engineered the quest for maritime security which relies on the use of national military and civil forces to patrol both international and local waterways, while international security supports through sets of frameworks and guidelines on the operations of national military strength in upholding maritime security as against the myriad of threats within the international water domain. The United Nations Convention of the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), the International Maritime Organization (IMO), and the Yaoundé Code of Conduct on maritime security in the Gulf of Guinea set foundational framework strategies for the use of collective force against identified threats facing both international and national waterways, and how national security approach of sovereign states should respond to the nature of threats within their waterway boundaries.

4.3. Maritime Threats to Nigeria Waterways

Maritime threats to our waterways have become extremely dangerous as this was identified by Feldt et.al (2014, p.23) stating the numerous threats militating the growth of activities along our waterways ranging from sea piracy, sea robbery, maritime terrorism, illicit trafficking by sea (narcotics and human trafficking), the proliferation of small arms and light weapons, and cargo theft are among major crimes and threat to our waterway. International conventions such as the law of the sea (UNCLOS) under article 101 comprehensively define threats to the maritime ecosystem as "any illegal acts of violence or detention, or any act of depression, committed for private ends by the crew or the passengers of a private ship, and directed: on the high seas, against another ship, or against person or property on board of such ship. Also, against any ship, person, or property in a place outside the jurisdiction of any state. Additionally, the international instrument identified piracy as any act of voluntary participation in the operation of a ship with knowledge of facts making it a pirate-ship. Additionally, any act of inciting or intentionally facilitating an act described before.

Conversely, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) additionally describes threats against maritime activities as "any illegal act of violence or detection or any act of depredation or threat thereof, other than an act of piracy committed for private ends and directed against a ship or against a person property on board such ship within a state domestic waters, archipelagic water and territorial sea. Also, any act of inciting or of intentionally facilitating an act described above" (Ifedi, 2020, p.224). In describing maritime terrorism, the Council for Security Cooperation in the Asia Pacific (CSCAP) conceptualized maritime terrorism as "the undertaking of terrorist acts and activities within the maritime environment, using or against vessels or fixed platforms at sea or in port of against any one of their passengers or personnel, against coastal facilities or settlements including tourist, resorts, port areas and port town or cities " (Ifedi, 2020 pp226). Therefore, with the classification of threats to the maritime domain listed by these organizations, what

constitutes threats to the Nigeria waterway is not far-fetched from the above-listed activities that undermine maritime activities. The current security threat experienced within the maritime domain in Nigeria includes acts of piracy, which is crafted or takes the dimension of violent attacks on maritime vessels, passengers, hostage kidnapping, sea robbery and fishing poaching.

Today, Nigeria with the international maritime sector are witnessing one of the oldest crimes against economic activities in the maritime domain, has been sea piracy. The sustainability of piracy both locally and internationally has been attributed to six factors.

Foremost, these factors have been linked to the massive increase in commercial maritime traffic within waterways and all seaports around the world. Secondly, the occurrence of seaborne commercial vessels that pass through narrow and congested maritime checkpoints. These hold-ups require ships to significantly reduce speed to ensure safe passage, which dramatically heightens their exposure to interception and attack.

A third dimension is the difficulties associated with maritime surveillance and the failure of the government to invest in expensive, satellite and sea-based surveillance tools. The Fourth reason includes the lax coastal and port-side security have played an important role in enabling low-level piratical activity, especially harbour thefts of goods from ships at anchor. The fifth dimension is the presence of corruption and poor judicial prerogative have encouraged official complicity in high-level pirate rings, which has impacted directly on the safety of vessels on our waterways. Finally, the global proliferation of small arms has provided pirates with an enhanced means to operate on a more destructive and sophisticated level.

Boris (2015, p.556) identified that piracy within Nigerian waterways is due to the prevalence of socio-economic, political, and infrastructural deficits. A statistical distribution adapted from the IMB piracy and Armed robbery against ships annual reports from 2003-2014 ranked the Nigeria waterways most unsafe maritime zone in the Gulf of Guinea. Nigeria was ranked about 55 percent with major maritime attacks against vessels (Ifesinachi et.al, 2015, p.8). A vivid example of piracy threats was the armed robbery attacks on patrol vessels of the joint task force in Robot Creek, in Nembe local government Area of Bayelsa state Nigeria, by approximately thirty armed robbers in two speed boats on June 24, 2014. The interception and hijacking of two passenger boats in Zion community of southern Ijaw local government area in Bayelsa in 2014, and pirate attacks on an oil rig in Gbarain in southern Ijaw local government area in Bayelsa state in 2014 (ibid, p.8) all these revealed the level of threats to the commercial and economic activities within the coastal region in Nigeria.

In 2021, the IMB Piracy Reporting Centre received 132 incidents of piracy and armed robbery against ships. Incidents comprise 115 vessels boarded, 11 attempted attacks, five vessels fired upon and one vessel hijacked. During the operational returns for 2nd quarterly meeting of the Nigerian Ports Consultative Council it was reported that from January 1 to June 30, 2024, it recorded 78 recorded across all ports in Nigeria to include seven accidents, four arrests, one assault, 13 cases of damage to its properties, seven deaths, two cases of arms and ammunition, and five fire incidents."

Moreover, in recent times, the threat to the maritime domain in Nigeria has reduced as the recent report put forward by the international Maritime Bureau (IMB) that Nigeria has recorded the least cases of piracy and sea robberies across its coastal water and attacks against ships in the Gulf of Guinea in the first half of 2022 (Sani,2021, p.1). Despite having a low spatial distribution of piracy activities in recent years, the effect of piracy on the economic viability of the waterways, remains an important threat to the sustainability of maritime transportation and trade interaction among states.

5. Theoretical Framework

This paper adopts the Marxist Political Economy paradigm as a tool for analyzing the connection of our waterways with the myriads of threats affecting the economic activities within the waterways. The Marxist paradigmatic orientation arose as a counterbalance to the central elitist political economy which was developed and popularized by Adam Smith and David Ricardo in the 18th century. This paradigmatic prism is propounded in Marx classical writings 1859, 1867, 1885, 1894. The political economy approach is based on dialectical materialism. The theory of dialectical materialism emphasizes the importance of material condition, the dynamic character of social reality and the relatedness of different elements of society (Ake 1981; Ifesinachi et.al, 2015, p.56).

The theory is premised on the notion that man is principally motivated by economic or material needs. Labour is the essence of material existence stating that economic activity is man's sole interest. To Marx, every political system

corresponds to and reflects its kind of economic structure. Thus, in the Preface to his work: "A Contribution to the Critique of Political Economy" Marx places quality on the sub-structural component of the society which plays a determinant role on other components such as politics, ideology, and culture. Therefore, from the substructure, one can easily understand the nature of internal relations, how a society organizes, manages, and reproduces itself, the causes of tension, conflicts, or contradictions in any given society as well as the direction of social change.

Similarly, Marx holds that the primary cause of tension and other social dislocation in a society is linked to economic factors. This he did when he utilized the political economy method for analyzing the root origins of conflicts and inconsistencies in the British capitalist economy. Corroborating the above argument, Akpuru-Aja (1998) asserts that "if one understands the economic structure of a society, the relations between the people in production process, it is easier to understand the nature of politics, culture, national security, socio-psychological consciousness, ideological inclinations" (Ifesinachi et.al,2015, p.56).

In relation to this study, the escalation of security threats along the maritime space, can be expressed within the view of the Marxist Political Economy. This approach also enables us to explain the failure of the government to effectively monitor economic activities that are carried out within the maritime domain and the waterways, and the elevation of the socio-economic well-being of coastal communities. Consequently, the neglect has led to the thriving of various maritime threats to businesses and economic activities carried out along the waterway. The proliferation of piracy, maritime terrorism, kidnapping and vessel and platform hijacking now thrive along these coastal areas. Additionally, the explosion of threats along our waterways and within the coastal areas is not entrenched in the mismanagement of economic resources, but also by profound political nonchalance of government. The prevalence of poor political leadership reinforced illegal maritime activities in the Nigerian and West Africa waterways. Despite the large deposit of hydrocarbon and Crude oil endowments, the prevalence of high rate of unemployment and low standard of living coupled with declining opportunities for legitimate occupation, youths who are unemployed or underemployed are now trooping in their numbers for recruitment into committing violent conflicts or take to piracy and other illicit activities for survival. The case of resource-conflicts in Nigeria's oil-rich Niger Delta region and Angola's Cabinda region arising from bad governance are similar.

6. Results and Discussions

6.1. Impact of Waterways on Nigeria's Economy

Findings revealed that Nigeria's maritime sector plays a crucial role in the country's economy, with about 80% of maritime economic activities in West Africa conducted in Nigeria. The sector contributes significantly to the country's GDP, with a direct impact of 3% in 2010. Nigeria trades about 180 million tons of sea-borne cargo per annum, with annual freight paid exceeding USD 6.8 billion. However, over 80% of this revenue is earned by foreign firms, resulting in significant capital flight, as the sector employs over 150,000 workers and generates estimated taxes of about fifteen billion dollars. Despite its economic importance, Nigeria is yet to fully harness the potentials of the maritime sector. The country loses huge revenues to foreign competitors, highlighting the need for indigenous participation and domination through local content provisions.

6.2. The Nexus between Waterways, National and International Security

The findings highlight the importance of security in the maritime ecosystem, which is crucial for the preservation of humanity, safety, and economic activities. This study also highlights the similitude of security objectives between national and international security, which is to ensure a threat-free maritime ecosystem. This is achieved through the combination of national power and international frameworks, guidelines, and procedures. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of maritime security, which relies on the use of national military and civil forces to patrol waterways, while international security supports this through frameworks and guidelines. The study references several international frameworks, including the United Nations Convention of the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), the International Maritime Organization (IMO), and the Yaoundé Code of Conduct on maritime security in the Gulf of Guinea. These frameworks provide strategies for using collective force against identified threats and guide national security approaches to respond to threats within their waterway boundaries.

6.3. Maritime Threats to Nigeria Waterways

Findings in this study revealed that Maritime threats to Nigeria's waterways are severe, including piracy, sea robbery, and maritime terrorism, illicit trafficking, and proliferation of small arms. These threats are attributed to factors such as increased commercial maritime traffic, congested maritime checkpoints, difficulties in maritime surveillance, lax

coastal and port-side security, corruption, and the global proliferation of small arms. Also, Piracy within Nigerian waterways is linked to socio-economic, political, and infrastructural deficits.

6.4. Methodology

The objective of this study is to examine the impact of Waterways on Nigeria's Economy, the nexus between waterways, National and International Security, and also, analyze the maritime threats to Nigeria's waterways. This study surveyed secondary data from existing literature drawn from empirical studies, reports, news contents, journals and other academic and professional materials that align with the subject matter.

7. Conclusion

The study underscores the critical nexus between Nigeria's waterways, national, and international security. Nigeria's maritime sector as a vital component of the country's economy, contributing significantly to its GDP and employing thousands of workers. However, the sector is plagued by severe maritime threats, including piracy, sea robbery, and maritime terrorism, which are attributed to various factors such as socio-economic, political, and infrastructural deficits. This study emphasizes the need for a combination of national power and international frameworks, guidelines, and procedures to ensure a threat-free maritime ecosystem

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made on the nexus between Nigerian waterways and, national and international security:

- **Enhance Indigenous Participation and Domination in the Maritime Sector:** The government should prioritize indigenous participation and domination in the maritime sector through local content provisions. This will help reduce capital flight, increase revenue generation, and promote economic growth.
- **Strengthen Maritime Security and Surveillance:** The government should invest in maritime surveillance and security infrastructure to combat maritime threats such as piracy, sea robbery, and maritime terrorism. This can be achieved through the acquisition of modern security equipment, training of personnel, and collaboration with international organizations.

Implement International Frameworks and Guidelines: The government should implement international frameworks and guidelines such as UNCLOS, IMO, and the Yaoundé Code of Conduct to ensure a threat-free maritime ecosystem. This will involve collaborating with neighboring countries and international organizations to share intelligence, coordinate responses to maritime threats, and develop strategies to prevent and respond to maritime security incidents.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All of the authors have declared that they have all participated in the design, execution, and analysis of the study and that they have approved the final version. Additionally, there are no conflicts of interest in connection with this study, and the material described is not under publication or consideration for publication elsewhere.

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